

Characterisation of ancient DNA preservation in human bone and teeth samples from Latvia with copper patination.

Version 0

Description

This DMP represents data obtained during a study concerned with effects of copper patination on ancient DNA preservation from archaeologically obtained human bones and teeth samples.

Funder

Central Finance and Contracting Agency Republic of Latvia

Grant

Consolidation of the Latvian Institute of Organic Synthesis and the Latvian Biomedical Research and Study Centre (5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/001.)

Researchers

Alise Pokšāne (orcid:0000-0002-5695-7798)

Organizations

Latvian Biomedical Research and Study Centre

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Characterisation of ancient DNA preservation in human bone and teeth samples from Latvia with copper patination.

Description:

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Researchers:

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Organizations:

Latvian Biomedical Research and Study Centre

Contact: Alise Pokšāne (alise.poksane@biomed.lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Central Finance and Contracting Agency Republic of Latvia

Grants: Consolidation of the Latvian Institute of Organic Synthesis and the Latvian Biomedical Research and Study Centre (5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/001.)

Project:

3. License

License:

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2024-09-20

4. Templates

Descriptions

Characterisation of ancient DNA preservation in human bone and teeth samples from Latvia with copper patination.

Dataset consists of shotgun sequencing data from archaeological bone and teeth samples with and without copper patination.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Shotgun sequencing data was collected in order to study the effects of copper patination on the preservation of ancient DNA.

Processed DNA was extracted from archaeological bone and tooth samples with and without copper patination.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

fastq

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

5.0

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No, because, to current knowledge, the topic of interest had not been previously researched and data generated are unique.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

Other

European Nucleotide Archive Project Accession Code: PRJEB79566

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

ENA default metadata checklist

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

European Nucleotide Archive

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Access to the internet.

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Data in this dataset is in the standard fastq format compatible with any other DNA data.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2024-09-20

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

There are no expenses, as the data is already freely accessible and FAIR.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Alise Pokšāne (orcid: [0000-0002-5695-7798](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5695-7798))

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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